

Bont Ticks, *Amblyomma hebraeum* & *A. variegatum*

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Amblyomma hebraeum (South African Bont Tick) and *A. variegatum* (Tropical Bont Tick) are two of the most widespread Bont ticks in southern Africa. *Amblyomma* spp. are beautifully ornate and iridescent (Fig. 1) three-host ticks with a diverse host range, including livestock and wildlife (Fig. 2).

Figure 1: Male *Amblyomma hebraeum*. Metallic iridescence is visible on the right-hand side. Photo: Alice Iddon, University of Liverpool

In recent years, veterinary professionals have noted changes in the distributions of these ticks, coinciding with changes in the spatial occurrence and epidemiology of tick-borne or tick-associated infections (e.g. [2]). A nationwide survey in 2024/25 conducted as part of the Kgofa project, confirmed range expansion of *A. variegatum* into Ngamiland in northwest Botswana (Fig. 3).

Figure 2: Three-host life-cycle of *Amblyomma hebraeum*/*Amblyomma variegatum*. Larvae (1), Nymphs (3) and Adults (5) in the environment seek a suitable host animal, attach (usually to hairless parts of the body) and feed. Larvae and nymphs detach when engorged (fully-fed; 2, 4) and moult to the next instar (life-cycle stage) in the environment. Adults mate on the host, and detach when engorged (6), laying eggs in the environment, which then hatch (7) completing the cycle. The host range of *Amblyomma hebraeum* (South African Bont Tick) and *Amblyomma variegatum* (Tropical Bont Tick) is broad; all stages feed on large mammals, whereas the larvae (and sometimes nymphs) also feed on birds, tortoises and smaller mammals such as scrub hare. [5]

Figure 3: Current known distribution of *A. hebraeum* and *A. variegatum* in Botswana and surrounding countries, based on historic records and a recent nationwide tick survey in Botswana (2024-2025, unpublished)

Tick-borne & associated diseases

A. hebraeum and *A. variegatum* are vectors for *Ehrlichia ruminantium*, the causative agent of heartwater in ruminants. Heartwater is endemic in southeast Botswana between Kanye/Jwaneng and Francistown [1].

Although not a tick-borne pathogen, *Dermatophilus congolensis* infection (dermatophilosis/Senkobo) is also associated with *A. variegatum*, likely due to tick-induced immunosuppression [3]. Dermatophilosis is widespread, but particularly problematic infections have been reported in Ngamiland, northwest Botswana, in recent years, coinciding with an apparent increase in the abundance of "Bont ticks" [2], which we have now confirmed to be *A. variegatum* (unpublished data; Fig. 3).

Control

A range of acaricides are licensed for chemical control of ticks in cattle and small ruminants, such as synthetic pyrethroid pour-ons, sprays and dips, but availability and quality of product varies by region [4]. Because *Amblyomma* spp. ticks spend the majority of their lifespan in the environment (Fig. 2), tick control on hosts is unlikely to eradicate a tick population, and treatments must be repeated. However, frequent acaricide use can lead to the development of resistance in the tick population, rendering the chemical treatments ineffective, or less effective [4]. Integrated control combines chemical control with other methods to reduce either the risk or consequences of infestation such as selecting tick-resistant breeds, manually removing ticks, or applying treatments during high risk periods, thus reducing re-

liance on the chemical acaricides. However, there is no one-size-fits-all approach, and the suite of options for integrated control must be tailored to the region and management system [4].

References

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